

**ETYMOLOGY OF THE TERM APHORISM AND THEORETICAL
CONSIDERATIONS ON THE PROBLEM**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14039755>

Abstract: In this article, the etymology of the term aphorism and the theoretical views on the issue are deeply analyzed. The first use of this term in science, aphorisms on various topics and their importance in our life are covered.

Keywords: aphorism, Heraclitus, John Gross, axiom, Oxford Book of Aphorisms

Abstract: In this article, the etymology of the term aphorism and the theoretical views on the issue are analyzed in depth. The first use of this term in science, aphorisms on various topics and their importance in our life are highlighted.

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Annotation: V dannoy state podzlo analiziruetsya etymologiya termina aforizm i teoreticheskie vzglyady na problemu. The enlightened first cases of the use of this term in science, aphorisms and different themes and ix meanings and nashey jizni.

Key words: aphorism, Heraclitus, John Gross, axiom, Oxford book aphorism.

Aphorism (Latin " aphorismus " and from the Greek words " aphorismós " - " aphorism ós " . come out) is this short , sharp and sure expressed thought or vital wisdom , often complicated ideas in lo and impressive way represents The term was first used by the Greek philosopher Heraclitus of Ephesus (given as Hippocrates on Wikipedia). Heraclitus used it for his short and vivid reflections on philosophical and natural phenomena .

Aphorisms can be on various topics, such as philosophy, politics, social issues, the nature of humanity, etc. They are distinguished by their brevity and depth, often allowing complex ideas to be expressed in a simple and understandable way.

Etymologically, the Greek word "aphorismós" means "to define", "to mark" or "to distinguish". This term was originally used in medicine to define and describe

diseases. Later, the term came to be used more broadly to mean any short, clear, and self-explanatory thought or reasoning.

When studying axioms in various sources, it is possible to observe the explanations given to aphorisms and their division into certain types. For example, in D. Kuronov's "Literary Dictionary" the aphorism is written as follows.

"APHORISM (Greek: aphorismos - definition, concise expression) - a general thought expressed in a concise form and effectively expressed by a known author. There are different definitions of aphorisms. In some sources, aphorisms must have a specific author, and this is said to be the main aspect that distinguishes them from proverbs, while in others this condition is not imposed. Aphorisms are different in terms of their appearance, and in some cases aphorisms are specially created, in which case it can be considered literally a genre. After all, in this case, it is a phenomenon of form that allows to express a generalized opinion on any issue based on the life experience of the creator.

A modern English collector of aphorisms, a well-known scientist John Gross (John Gross) in his anthology "Oxford Book of Aphorisms" writes about the etymology of aphorism as follows.

"The earliest aphorisms, at least those bearing this name, were a collection of short medical teachings and sayings of Hippocrates. The term was re-circulated during the Renaissance, and, as originally, the word was used in the field of exact sciences.

Originally, semantically, the term "aphorism" corresponded to the word axiom - a truth that does not require proof - used in today's exact sciences. Because its old explanation is defined as Oxford "concise statement of a principle" ("a short explanation of a principle in any field of science") . An axiom is usually a short, clear, and fact-based statement or opinion. Axioms can be observed in mathematics, physics and other scientific fields .

By the early 18th century, the physician and teacher Richard Blackmore described the Hippocratic aphorisms as nothing more than a "joke book" but a book of worldly wisdom and manners. This blunder allowed Johnson to make a brief account of Blackmore's scientific knowledge in Lives of the Poets.

Aphorisms are usually more subversive. In fact, they often aim to be disruptive. One should think about the labels that most of them saw the light for the first time - observations, reflections, "discoveries", "separate thoughts". Others began life in fragments, such as notebook notes or random perceptions.

We can all agree that the most obvious characteristic of an aphorism, apart from its brevity, is that it is a generalization. It describes certain recurring aspects of life expressed in terms that should be constant and universally applicable. But the same can be said about proverbs, and aphorisms, unlike proverbs, have authors. A third distinguishing feature of an aphorism is that it is, in fact, a form of literature, and often a form that is unique or self-conscious. It bears the stamp and style of the mind that created it, its message universal but hardly personal; it may contain strong enough turns of thought to retain its force in translation, but it is the thin or concentrated expression of the phrase that can sometimes approach poetry to its full effect on verbal art. depending on perfection. At the same time, it should be added that brevity is not the highest stylistic quality in an aphorism, and the best examples are not always the shortest. A good aphorism is here also different from a proverb that should slide.

The aphorism, finally, should appear on its own. It's what Johnson describes as a "no-strings-attached" proposition. Nevertheless, in practice, many aphorisms are retorts and ripostes aimed at proponents of established viewpoints or shallow morals. Sometimes the aphorism itself seems to lend itself to a fascinating view of human nature. Trying to distance himself from nonsense, the aphorist is drawn towards a disturbing paradox. Forced to deal with his wits in a narrow compass, he revels in absurdity.

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